

Sample 31a

Greyscale Image

PARC Phases

	area %
{Pb-rich}	0.0000
{Si}	57.5
{Mg, Si}	8.5
{Mg, Al, Si}	7.5
{Al, Si}	6.3
{Na, Al, Si}	3.6
{Ca}	2.5
{Al, Si, K}	2.5
{Mg, Ca}	2.0
{Fe}	1.4
{Si, Ca LoP}	1.3
{Na, Si}	1.1
{Na, Si, Cl}	0.8
{Si, Ca HIP}	0.7
{Al, Si, Ca}	0.5
{Mg}	0.4
{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.4
{Si, K}	0.4
{Cl}	0.3
{Si, Cl}	0.3
{Si, Fe}	0.2
{S, Ca}	0.2
{Ti}	0.2
{Cl}	0.2
{Mg, Al, Si, Ca}	0.1
{Si, Fe}	0.1
{Si, S, Ca}	0.1
{Al}	0.1
{Na, Al, Si, Cl}	0.1
{Ca, Fe}	0.1
{Al, Ca}	0.1
{Mg, Si, Cl}	0.1
{Na, Mg, Si, Cl}	0.0
{Zn-LA1}	0.0
{Cr, Fe}	0.0

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	0.3
Pellet	0.0
Ore preparation undifferentiated	1.1
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.0
Ore / hot metal	0.0
BOF converter slag	0.0
BOF converter slag slopping	0.4
Slag BOF converter or desulph	0.0
Desulph slag	0.0
Ca-aluminate slag	0.0
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	2.5
Olivine flux	2.5
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	1.0
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.0
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
Tundish gunning mass	0.5
Alumina	0.0
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.0
Fe-metal rich	0.0
Coal and cokes or soil	5.3
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	0.0
Carbon rich - other	0.7
Cement or BOF converter	0.9
Cement	1.8
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.0
Ti-rich paint	0.0
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.2
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.0
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	68.3
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	14.2
Misc silicates including natural	0.4
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
Na-sulphate rich	0.0
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	0.0

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	1.4
Site - ore / hot metal	0.0
Site - slag	0.4
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	5.0
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.0
Site - flux / slag	1.0
Site - flux / refractory	0.0
Site - refractory	0.5
Site - scrap	0.0
Urban + site - scrap	0.0
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	5.3
Site - carbon-rich other	0.0
Site - carbon-rich other, + natural + urban	0.7
Urban, rarely site - slag	0.9
Urban	2.0
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	68.3
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	14.2
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.4
Unknown	0.0
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	0.0

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Sample 31b

Greyscale Image

PARC Phases

		area %
	{Pb-rich}	0.0001
	{Si}	54.4
	{Mg, Al, Si}	8.7
	{Al, Si}	8.2
	{Mg, Si}	7.8
	{Al, Si, K}	3.9
	{Ca}	2.4
	{Na, Al, Si}	2.3
	{Fe}	1.8
	{Mg, Ca}	1.4
	{Si, Ca LoP}	1.1
	{Na, Si, Cl}	1.0
	{Na, Si}	0.9
	{S, Ca}	0.7
	{Si, K}	0.7
	{Si, Ca HIP}	0.6
	{Al, Si, Ca}	0.4
	{Cl}	0.4
	{Si, Cl}	0.3
	{Mg}	0.3
	{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.3
	{Si, Fe}	0.3
	{Cl}	0.2
	{Ti}	0.2
	{Mg, Fe}	0.2
	{Si, S, Ca}	0.2
	{S}	0.1
	{Na, Al, Si, Cl}	0.1
	{Si, Fe}	0.1
	{Al}	0.1
	{Zn-LA1}	0.0
	{Mg, Al, Si, Ca}	0.0
	{S, Ba-LA1}	0.0
	{Ca, Fe}	0.0
	{Mg, Al, Si, K}	0.0

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	0.0
Pellet	0.5
Ore preparation undifferentiated	1.3
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.0
Ore / hot metal	0.0
BOF converter slag	0.4
BOF converter slag slopping	0.0
Slag BOF converter or desulph	0.2
Desulph slag	0.0
Ca-aluminate slag	0.0
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	1.7
Olivine flux	2.7
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	0.9
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.3
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.0
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.0
Fe-metal rich	0.0
Coal and cokes or soil	7.2
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	0.4
Carbon rich - other	1.3
Cement or BOF converter	0.9
Cement	2.9
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.4
Ti-rich paint	0.2
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.4
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.0
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-day-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	71.6
Qz-day-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	6.4
Misc silicates including natural	0.0
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
Na-sulphate rich	0.0
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	0.3

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	1.8
Site - ore / hot metal	0.0
Site - slag	0.6
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	4.4
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.0
Site - flux / slag	0.9
Site - flux / refractory	0.3
Site - refractory	0.0
Site - scrap	0.0
Urban + site - scrap	0.0
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	7.2
Site - carbon-rich other	0.4
Site - carbon-rich other, + natural + urban	1.3
Urban, rarely site - slag	0.9
Urban	3.9
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	71.6
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	6.4
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.0
Unknown	0.0
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	0.3

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Sample 31c

Greyscale Image

PARC Phases

		area %
	{Pb-rich}	0.0005
	{Si}	59.7
	{Mg, Si}	7.9
	{Al, Si}	6.9
	{Mg, Al, Si}	6.0
	{Ca}	3.0
	{Na, Al, Si}	2.6
	{Al, Si, K}	2.2
	{Mg, Ca}	1.4
	{Fe}	1.2
	{Si, Ca LoP}	1.1
	{Na, Si}	1.0
	{Na, Si, Cl}	0.8
	{Mg}	0.7
	{Al, Si, Ca}	0.6
	{Si, Ca HIP}	0.6
	{Si, K}	0.5
	{S, Ca}	0.5
	{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.5
	{Cl}	0.3
	{Si, Fe}	0.3
	{Si, Cl}	0.3
	{Cl}	0.3
	{Si, S, Ca}	0.2
	{P, Ca}	0.1
	{Al}	0.1
	{Ti}	0.1
	{Al, S}	0.1
	{Na, Al, Si, Cl}	0.1
	{S}	0.1
	{Mg, Al, Si, Ca}	0.1
	{Si, Fe}	0.1
	{Al, Ca}	0.0
	{Mg, Si, Cl}	0.0
	{Si, Ca, Ti}	0.0

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	0.1
Pellet	0.3
Ore preparation undifferentiated	0.3
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.0
Ore / hot metal	0.0
BOF converter slag	0.3
BOF converter slag slopping	0.0
Slag BOF converter or desulph	0.3
Desulph slag	0.0
Ca-aluminate slag	0.0
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	1.5
Olivine flux	4.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	1.2
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.9
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.1
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.0
Fe-metal rich	0.0
Coal and cokes or soil	7.1
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	0.5
Carbon rich - other	0.8
Cement or BOF converter	0.6
Cement	1.9
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.2
Ti-rich paint	0.0
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.2
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.0
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-day-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	70.6
Qz-day-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	8.9
Misc silicates including natural	0.0
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.1
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
Na-sulphate rich	0.0
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.1
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	0.0

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	0.7
Site - ore / hot metal	0.0
Site - slag	0.5
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	5.4
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.0
Site - flux / slag	1.2
Site - flux / refractory	0.9
Site - refractory	0.1
Site - scrap	0.0
Urban + site - scrap	0.0
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	7.1
Site - carbon-rich other	0.5
Site - carbon-rich other; + natural + urban	0.8
Urban; rarely site - slag	0.6
Urban	2.3
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	70.6
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	8.9
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.1
Unknown	0.0
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/o partial chloride cover)	0.1

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels